

A Portable Multi-Parameter Fluid Monitoring Unit for Real-Time Measurements During Well Development and Geothermal Operations

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Abstract

Monitoring of fluid parameters during well development, groundwater production, or geothermal operation is essential for the understanding of subsurface and well processes. We developed *FluMoMax*, a portable fluid monitoring unit, that can measure several physicochemical parameters in real-time, to monitor fluid characteristics and to enable early detection of geochemical processes such as scaling, corrosion, particle mobilization, and oxygen intrusion. *FluMoMax* integrates sensors for continuous measurement of pH, oxidation–reduction potential, specific electrical conductivity, dissolved oxygen, temperature, turbidity, and density. Optical changes of the fluid can be visually observed through a sighting tube. Various valves are installed for fluid sampling or connecting additional monitoring devices. For high turbidity water, particle filters can be connected. The inline pump regulates the flow rate and ensures backflow without pressure loss into the main production or injection flow line. The device is designed for use in the field, for example, at drilling and well sites. It can operate at process temperatures of up to 120 °C and pressures of up to 10 bar, and was first tested at a drilling site in Berlin under temperatures of up to 107 °C and pressures of up to 7 bar, demonstrating operational reliability for field deployment. *FluMoMax* provides a robust, and modular solution for multi-parameter monitoring, thereby improving the understanding of hydrogeochemical dynamics during groundwater extraction and injection.

Introduction

A continuous monitoring of physicochemical parameters in aqueous solutions during well development, groundwater production, and geothermal operation is essential for understanding geochemical and biological processes and maintaining well performance. Parameters such as pH, oxidation–reduction potential (ORP), specific electrical conductance (EC), dissolved oxygen (DO), turbidity, and density can provide key information about physicochemical reactions that take place during well development and fluid production. This allows, for example, taking representative groundwater samples to distinguish extracted fluid from formation water and residuals from the drilling process or

standing borehole water, and verify real-time stabilization criteria (ISO 2014; USGS 2018). It is particularly important to continuously monitor these parameters during well development to determine when the composition of the produced water represents the undisturbed formation water (Barcelona et al. 2005).

Changes in pH, EC, DO, ORP, turbidity, and density may indicate the stage of development and the presence of residues of the drilling process (Regenspurg et al. 2018). Robust baseline monitoring is essential for evaluating geochemical changes, the operational impact, and the scope of regeneration activities in water supply and geothermal systems. Continuous monitoring is particularly important within thermal-influenced systems. Temperature changes significantly impact geochemical and microbial processes, such as scaling, corrosion, and biofilm formation (Kristmannsdóttir et al. 2012; Mundhenk et al. 2013). Real-time measurements of physicochemical parameters enable early detection of changes and facilitate rapid adjustments to well regeneration and operational procedures. Previous monitoring devices have demonstrated the value of constant measurements in geothermal plants, revealing significant fluid property alterations during initial operation (Feldbusch et al. 2013; Milsch et al. 2013). However, monitoring geothermal and other extreme environments during well development is technically challenging. When extracting water from freshly drilled or unconsolidated aquifers, large amounts of suspended fines,

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drilling residues, particles and sand are typically mobilized. This clogs flow paths in monitoring systems and damages sensors. Additionally, high fluid temperatures and salinity in geothermal and high-temperature aquifer thermal energy systems (HT-ATES) require robust, heat-resistant components. These conditions make it difficult to achieve stable, continuous flow-through monitoring, as well as to determine the optimal time for representative fluid sampling.

The FluMoMax fluid monitoring unit was developed to meet these challenges. It bridges the gap between environmental field instruments and high-temperature process monitoring. This compact system is designed for mobile use and integrates sensors for simultaneous, multi-parameter measurements in a closed loop, as well as a sampling spot. The sensors are protected from particle contamination by an integrated filter unit, and heat-resistant components allow operation at temperatures above 100 °C. Its modular design makes it compatible with site-specific setups, and it is ideal for well development and baseline measurements, as well as for geothermal and HT-ATES monitoring.

Concept and Design

System Overview

FluMoMax is a modular bypass system that can be connected to the main production/injection line of a well or a water pipeline (Figure 1). Water is purged through the unit and back to the main line downstream in a closed system via ½" stainless steel corrugated hoses, without pressure loss or contact with the atmosphere. The flow rate *Q* (liters per minute) is controlled via a flowmeter and an auxiliary pump that can be added modularly. All components except the turbidity sensor (which can be bypassed at >85 °C and 6 bar)

are designed for 10 bar and 120 °C, allowing monitoring within a wide range of field applications. Only corrosion-resistant materials were used to enable also the monitoring of saline brines over a long period of time. The unit consists mainly of two separate flow-through modules, one frequency converter, one data logger, and one box containing the sensors and cables, allowing easy transportation of the device. Each module is connected via quick-connect high-pressure fittings, enabling setup within minutes.

Flow Path and Component Arrangement

The unit is designed to bypass the main flow line, as shown in Figure 2, and comprises various components for measurement and *Q* control, starting with the turbidity flow-through cell. This cell is equipped with a turbidity sensor for continuous measurement of the particle load and suspended solids. It can be bypassed when exceeding the process limits. A 10 cm sighting tube follows the sensor, enabling visual monitoring of the fluid. This component allows qualitative real-time monitoring of any optical changes, including fluid color, gas bubbles, and mineral precipitation (scaling). A pressure gauge in the downstream fluid path enables pressure monitoring. It provides information on system pressure and indicates malfunctions, such as filter clogging or pump defects, by displaying increased values. There are two sampling valves positioned upstream of the filters. These can be used to take unfiltered fluid samples, for example, for gas, chemical, and microbiological analysis. The filter unit consists of two replaceable parallel filter cartridges (with a mesh size of 10 µm or 50 µm), which allow undisturbed continuous monitoring while one filter is being changed and cleaned. The whole filter unit can also be bypassed when there is no need for filtration due to low-particle fluid. Two additional sampling valves enable pre-filtered fluid

Figure 1. Fluid monitoring unit FluMoMax in operation at a drilling site connected to the main production line. Modules I and II house the measurement sensors and pump. The frequency converter and data logger are located on the left. The stainless steel inflow and outflow pipes are wrapped in black insulation material to protect operators from high fluid temperatures (here, up to 105 °C).

Figure 2. Schematic of the flow-through line including all sensors and sampling spots within the fluid monitoring system. Module I contains the main measurement cell with pH, ORP, EC, DO sensors, densimeter, and flowmeter. Module II houses the turbidity sensor and the pump.

Table 1
Main Sensor Component Specifications

Parameter	Measuring range	Resolution	Accuracy	Max Pressure (bar)	Max Temp. (°C)
pH	0–14	0.01	±0.1	17	135
ORP	–1000 to 1000 mV	0.1	±5 mV	17	135
EC	0.001–500 mS/cm	0.001	±1%	17	120
DO	0.01–30 mg/L	0.001	±1%	13	140
Turbidity	40–4000 FAU	0.1	±2%	6	85
Density	0.8–1.3 g/cm ³	1 × 10 ^{–4}	±2 × 10 ^{–4}	50	150
Temperature	–25 to 150 °C	0.1	0.1 K	50	150
Pressure	0–25 bar	1	0.5 bar	25	200
Flowmeter	0.2–100 L/min	0.01	±3%	40	180
Pump	0–14.5 L/min	0.1 Hz	–	34	176
Measuring cell	–	–	–	10	150

sampling. It can be used as an alternative sampling spot if the particle load is too high and clogs the microbiological filters too quickly, for example. The density gauge with an oscillating U-tube is followed. This sensor quantifies fluid density as an important parameter, influenced by temperature and salinity, and monitors, among others, the mixing of fluids. The integrated temperature sensor enables simultaneous temperature measurement for density correction. A flowmeter for measuring the bypass Q follows. The primary multi-parameter flow-through measurement cell is the last unit on the rack and is set up with probes for pH, ORP, DO, EC measurements, and integrated temperature sensors. This main unit enables key hydrogeochemical parameters to be monitored simultaneously in a flow-through chamber, while also ensuring that the flow continues past the probe and prevents contact with the atmosphere. Positioning the electrodes after the filters protects them from particles and ensures stable measurement conditions. The system hydraulics are maintained by a gear pump that is controlled by a frequency converter. This pump enables a regulated bypass Q, regardless of fluctuations in line pres-

sure, and ensures that fluid returns to the downstream main line without any pressure loss.

Sensor Integration and Data Acquisition

The central 8-channel analog data acquisition unit collects and processes all sensor data. The integrated data logger network interface allows the measuring transducers to record and store measured values. It ensures the continuous data recording and can be connected to a laptop or tablet via a LAN cable. Real-time visualization of the data is possible with export formats of .csv and .xml.

Technical Specifications and Capabilities

FluMoMax integrates high-grade, robust sensors that have been selected for use in challenging environments, such as those encountered in water supply, drilling operations, and geothermal applications. These sensors can withstand high temperatures, pressure, and salinity (Tables 1 and 2).

Table 2
Wetted Material Specifications and Components

FluMoMax Components	Material (AISI/EN/DIN If Applicable)
Capillaries, valves, fittings, flexible hoses, turbidity sensor process connection, pressure gauge connection, filter housings, filter cartridges, multi-parameter flow cell, flowmeter housing, and various structural parts	316L/1.4404/X2CrNiMo17-12-2
DO and EC sensor shaft and spot cap	316L/1.4435/X2CrNiMo18-14-3
Turbidity sensor body	316Ti/1.4571/X6CrNiMoTi17-12-2
Flowmeter measuring tube	304/1.4301/X5CrNi18-10
Oscillating tube of the densitometer, flowmeter electrodes, gear pump housing, and pump shaft	Alloy C-276/2.4819/NiMo16Cr15W
pH/ORP sensor membrane and body, conductivity sensor ceramic elements	Glass and ceramic metal oxide
pH/ORP sensor electrode, conductivity sensor electrodes, Pt1000 temperature sensors	Platinum
sighting tube	Polycarbonate
Turbidity sensor head (PCTFE); pump gears and bearings (PEEK); flowmeter lining (PFA); seals and O-rings (EPDM, FKM, PTFE)	High-performance polymers

Sensor Specifications, Sensor Accuracy, and Calibration Accuracy

Turbidity measurements are performed using the Endress+Hauser Turbimax CUS50D absorption sensor (Endress+Hauser 2023). The measuring principle relies on light attenuation according to ISO 7027 (ISO 2016) using a wavelength of 860 nm. An infrared LED emits light through the measuring path within the sensor, and an opposing detector quantifies the attenuation of the transmitted light intensity. Turbidimetry was chosen for measuring light attenuation over nephelometry because it is more applicable to medium-to-highly turbid waters (ISO 2016). Such waters are particularly encountered during well development and remediation. This measuring range is factory-calibrated within the range of 40 to 4000 FAU (formazin absorption units), but the maximum working range is from 0 to 10,000 FAU and from 0 to 60 g/L solid content, depending on the measurement application. The measurement accuracy is $\pm 10\%$ or ± 10 FAU, whichever is greater. The sensor is made for temperatures up to 85 °C and 6 bar. Although single-point calibration is sufficient, the sensor has been pre-calibrated at the factory. The *pressure* can be monitored via an analogue manometer (Swagelok) with a measuring range between 0 and 25 bar. *Density* is measured after the filter unit using an Anton Paar DPRn 427HT density meter (Paar 2013). This device uses the oscillating U-tube method to determine the fluid density. The tube, which is filled with the flowing fluid, is electromagnetically excited to oscillate in its characteristic density-dependent frequency. *Temperature* measurement is integrated via a Pt100 thermo-sensor and transmitted alongside the frequency signal to an mPDS 1100 evaluation unit (Paar 2009), where the density is calculated. The density measuring range extends from 0 to 3 g/cm³ (measurement accuracy 0.0001 g/cm³) and the temperature measuring range lies between -25 and 150 °C (accuracy <0.1 K). The pressure limits are 50 bar. Calibrations and verifications are performed using certified reference materials, typically with ultrapure, degassed water and dry air or vacuum as primary standards, as well as application-specific liquid standards. *Flow rate* is measured using a Proline

Promag electromagnetic flowmeter from Endress+Hauser (Endress+Hauser 2018). This consists of a sensor, which is installed in the fluid path, and a separate transmitter for signal processing. The measuring principle is based on Faraday's law of induction: moving charge carriers in the electrically conductive fluid induce a voltage that is proportional to the flow velocity and is detected by electrodes. The measuring range covers flow velocities from 0.1 to 10 m/s, corresponding to Q from 0.5 to 10 L/min. Accuracy is $\pm 0.5\%$ of the measured value. The sensor is designed for temperatures ranging from -40 to 180 °C and pressures of up to 40 bar. This method is independent of viscosity and density, and does not cause any pressure loss. The main measurement unit comprises a flow cell (Flowfit CPA240 Endress+Hauser) equipped with three Memosens digital sensors. *pH* measurement is performed using the Endress+Hauser Memosens CPS16E: a combined glass electrode featuring an Ag/AgCl reference system and an integrated NTC 30K temperature sensor (Endress+Hauser 2025b). The measuring principle is based on potentiometric detection of H⁺ activity by the pH-sensitive glass membrane. The membrane glass of the sensor provides an electrochemical potential through the selective accumulation of H⁺ ions on its outer layer. This creates an electrochemical boundary layer with an electrical potential difference. The integrated Ag/AgCl reference system acts as the required reference electrode. The measured voltage is converted into the corresponding pH value according to the Nernst equation. The measuring range extends from pH 0 to 14, with a resolution of 0.01 pH and an accuracy of ± 0.1 pH. Calibration is performed using NIST buffer solutions at pH 4, 7, and 10, either two- or three-point. The *redox potential* is simultaneously measured with the platinum electrode in the Memosens CPS16E (Endress+Hauser 2025b). This measurement refers to the Ag/AgCl reference system with an ion trap and a 3M KCl bridge electrolyte. The measuring range extends from -2000 to +2000 mV, with a resolution of 0.1 mV and an accuracy of ± 5 mV. Calibration is performed using a reference solution of 220 mV at pH 7. For hydrogeochemical evaluations and thermodynamic calculations,

conversion to the standard hydrogen potential is required. This conversion is temperature-dependent with the following empirical equation, where coefficient a is 50,230 and b is 295 for sensor type Ag/AgCl KCl 3 mol/L, T is the measured temperature [°C], and ORP_{meas} is the measured redox potential (Wolkersdorfer 2008):

$$E_H = ORP_{meas} [mV] - 0.198 \times (T [^{\circ}C] - 25) + \sqrt{(a - b \times T)} \quad (1)$$

This sensor is designed for process temperatures ranging from 0 to 135 °C and pressures of up to 17 bar. The *specific electrical conductivity* is measured using a four-electrode Endress+Hauser Memosens CLS82E sensor with integrated Pt1000 temperature sensor (Endress+Hauser 2024). Alternating current is applied via the outer pair of electrodes, and the voltage between the inner pair is measured. This determines the electrolytic conductivity of the fluid between the electrodes. The measurement range is from 1 μS/cm to 500 mS/cm, with an accuracy of <2% up to 1 mS/cm and <4% up to 500 mS/cm. Sensor drift is verified using a reference solution within the same range as the measured fluid, for example, 1.46, 12.64, 50, or 107 mS/cm. The sensor's temperature limits are 120 °C at a pressure of up to 17 bar. The Memosens COS81E optical sensor (Endress+Hauser) is used to measure *dissolved oxygen* (Endress+Hauser 2025a). Operating on the principle of luminescence quenching, it uses oxygen-sensitive dyes that alter their emission decay time in response to oxygen concentration. Measuring range extends from 0.01 to 30 mg/L, with a resolution of 0.001 mg/L. The measurement deviation is ±1% of the measured value or ±8 μg/L, whichever is greater. Calibration can be performed as a zero-point calibration in an oxygen-free medium, or as a one-point calibration in air. A Pt1000 temperature sensor is integrated. The process fluid temperature range is 0 to 140 °C, with a maximum pressure of 13 bar. Prior to use in the field, all sensors should undergo laboratory calibration using certified reference standards. A new calibration or sensor drift check must be performed in the field immediately before the start of the measurements. During operation, daily to weekly verifications using test solutions are needed to detect drifts. If there is a deviation of more than 5% from the target value, the sensors must be recalibrated. After the monitoring, a post-sensor drift check must be performed.

After fieldwork, the system should be flushed with fresh water, especially when operating with saline fluids, to prevent salt precipitation and corrosion in the flow path. Depending on the type of contamination, the sensors should be rinsed with fresh water, a fat solvent or a dilute acid. Seals and O-rings must be routinely inspected to ensure system integrity.

Operational Capabilities

The FluMoMax is designed for continuous measurements in the field. The process temperature ranges from -5 to 120 °C for almost all components, except the turbidity sensor, which can only tolerate up to 85 °C and must be bypassed at exceeding these temperatures. The bypass

is integrated into the FluMoMax system (Figure 2). The measurement devices have protection classes ranging from IP66 to IP68, making them suitable for outdoor use in normal weather conditions. The pump housing has IP55 protection, which provides limited protection, so additional cover is required during heavy or prolonged rainfall. The transmitter and data logger are protected against rainwater inside the case; however, the power connections must be protected from moisture and rain separately. The maximum operating pressure of the system is 10 bar. If the main line pressure exceeds this value, the built-in valves must be manually operated to regulate and lower the pressure to an acceptable level, as indicated by the manometer. However, the gear pump (Verder VGS870) ensures continuous Q through the measurement unit and back to the main line. Q can be regulated via the frequency converter (Hitachi L200), with an optimal Q between 1 and 10 L/min. The data logger (Meier NT ADL MXmini), which is integrated like the multimeter transducer (Liquiline CM448, Endress+Hauser) in the case, allows configurable measurement frequencies of up to one measurement per second. This enables high-resolution monitoring of hydrogeochemical processes. For long-term monitoring applications, lower sampling frequencies can be selected. Two standard mains connections (230 V) are required for the frequency converter and the multi-parameter transmitter. An optional third connection is needed for a laptop or tablet, which can be used for real-time visualization, system configuration and data transfer.

Material Selection for Corrosion Resistance

Working with high-salinity fluid at elevated temperatures requires the selection of corrosion-resistant materials to ensure system integrity and data quality (Table 2). All capillaries, valves, and fittings are made of type 316L stainless steel. The flexible, corrugated 1/2" stainless steel pipes that connect the different modules to each other and to the main line are made from the same material. The turbidity sensor's process connection is also made of 316L stainless steel, while the sensor head is made of polychlorotrifluoroethylene (PCTFE) and the sensor body is made of 316Ti stainless steel. The sighting tube is made of high-viscosity polycarbonate. Both the pressure gauge connection and the filter housing and cartridges are made of stainless steel (316L). The U-tube of the density meter is made of alloy C-276. The measurement tube of the flowmeter is made of stainless steel (304) with a PFA (perfluoroalkoxy) lining. The measurement sensor is made of alloy C-276, and the flowmeter housing and multi-parameter flow-through cell are made of stainless steel 316L. The pH/ORP combination electrode has a glass membrane and body. The conductivity probe consists of platinum and ceramics. The shaft and spot cap of this probe, as well as that of the oxygen sensor, are made of stainless steel type 316L. All temperature sensors are made of platinum, and the gear pump housing and pump shaft are made of alloy C-276, whereas the pump gears and bearings are made of PEEK (polyether ether ketone). All seals and O-rings are made out of high-performance polymers.

Figure 3. Time series of parameters measured by FluMoMax during the well development (red dots) and the main production line (pink dots). Gray shaded areas highlight the pumping intervals. High turbidity values indicate particle mobilization during each pumping cycle. Temperature measurements show readings from both the wellhead (pink dots) and the FluMoMax sensor (red dots), while the flow rate Q of the main production line is shown in the bottom diagram, measured by a separate pressure gauge.

Field Application

The following examples demonstrate the system’s operational reliability and performance under challenging field

conditions. FluMoMax was successfully tested during well development and hydraulic tests at a freshly drilled side track of the 456-m-deep exploration well in Berlin, Ger-

Figure 4. Time series of parameters continuously measured by FluMoMax during hot push-pull tests with elevated temperature. The gray shaded areas mark the production and injection intervals, and the white area marks the break in between. Temperature measurements are shown as pink dots for the wellhead and as red dots for the FluMoMax sensor. The flow rate Q of the main production line is measured by a separate pressure gauge and displayed on the diagram at the bottom.

many (Norden et al. 2023), which targeted a Hettangian sandy aquifer at a depth of between 360 and 390 m bgs.

Well Development and Hydraulic Testing

During the seven-day well development, FluMoMax was installed on site to continuously monitor the fluid properties and collect samples. Figure 3 shows the measurement data during 1 day of well development. The well was developed by repeatedly extracting water at a high frequency over a short time period. The high turbidity observed during each pumping interval indicates the mobilization of particles from the area near the filter screen during the well development. The increased dissolved oxygen concentration, particularly at the beginning, is attributed to disconnecting the inflow and outflow pipes, changing the filters, or checking sensor drifts. Specific electrical conductivity oscillates at the start of each measurement interval due to the presence of particles smaller than the filter mesh of 10 or 50 μm . pH and ORP values did not stabilize due to the short pumping intervals of just a few minutes. The density and temperature data show repetitive values during continuous flow.

Continuous Monitoring During Hot Push–Pull Test

A hot push–pull test (Blöcher et al. 2024) was performed at the same drilling site, with injection temperatures reaching 107 °C. FluMoMax monitored fluid parameters during production and injections continuously over a period of 3 weeks, providing a detailed data set. Despite the harsh conditions, such as consistently high temperatures, minimal maintenance work was required, with essentially only slight sensor drift occurring (<5% deviation of standards). Figure 4 demonstrates a 24-h measurement interval from the hydraulic field tests. The final hours of production show a consistent sensor response across all parameters, capturing the physicochemical changes of the produced fluid as it cooled during the production phase. After a five-hour break, the injection of formation water that had been stored at the surface from the former production phase began. Switching the inflow and outflow pipes of the FluMoMax unit enabled oxygen ingress, shown by the increased concentrations of dissolved oxygen in the fluid. Opening the sampling valve for a few minutes increased Q of FluMoMax and caused the oxygen level to decrease. Once the dissolved oxygen concentration had decreased below 0.05 mg/L (the water was considered oxygen-free, accounting for sensor calibration and measurement noise), the injection of the water into the aquifer began. The turbidity sensor had to be bypassed once the temperature reached 85 °C. Opening the valves for sampling caused a brief reduction in Q. The device was operating continuously for up to 5 weeks without any sensor failure. Maintenance requirements were low, with daily to weekly sensor drift check proving sufficient and no need for sensor calibration or replacement during the campaign (with deviation from standards of less than 5%).

Conclusion

We have designed and constructed a fluid monitoring system that enables the continuous and representative measure-

ment of key physicochemical parameters in real-time in a closed bypass. Through the monitoring of turbidity, density, pH, ORP, EC, DO, and temperature, as well as visual properties, comprehensive fluid characterization is possible at temperatures of up to 120 °C and pressures of up to 10 bar. FluMoMax was successfully tested during hydraulic tests at a freshly drilled well under challenging conditions of 107 °C fluid temperature, high salinity (60 mS/cm), oxygen-free water, and partly high particle load. This system offers a reliable and robust unit for characterization of hydrobiogeochemical processes, designed for geothermal monitoring and well development but can also be used in other environments such as aquifer storage and recovery systems, mine water monitoring, and groundwater remediation sites. The modular design allows for adaptation to site-specific requirements. All components except the sighting tube are commercially available, enabling replication by other research groups and plant operators.

Future improvements could address the system's current temperature limitations. Extending the operating temperature range beyond 120 °C using high-temperature sensor variants would enable monitoring in deeper geothermal systems. Additionally, installing venting valves on the filters would prevent oxygen ingress after replacement. Lastly, integrated carrying handles would make it easier for field personnel to transport the system's modular components, making the 60-min setup process more ergonomic.

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Declaration of Generative AI and AI-Assisted Technologies in the Writing Process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used machine learning–based translator and writing assistance [DeepL] in order to correct the grammar of the text. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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